

3D TRANSMISSION ELECTRON MICROSCOPY TO QUANTIFY THE MORPHOLOGY OF ALIGNED NANOFIBER NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in fabricating controlled-morphology, aligned carbon nanotube (A-CNT) assemblies with high (20% and above) volume fraction (V_f) create unique opportunities for markedly improving the performance of the next-generation advanced materials. These performance improvements are due to the scale-dependent and intrinsic properties of the CNTs themselves, and the ability to transfer their anisotropic properties to the polymer nanocomposites (PNC). However, a range of experimentally determined properties of such advanced PNCs are not in agreement with theoretical predictions. This fact strongly suggests that the initial assumptions about the PNC structure may be inaccurate. Here we present new 3-dimensional (3D) measurements of the nanoscale morphology of polymer materials containing high V_f of A-CNTs as revealed using energy-filtered electron tomography. We quantify the evolution of CNT morphology and state of dispersion with increasing V_f in terms of network structure, alignment, bundling and waviness and find that increasing the A-CNT V_f results in a nonlinear increase in bundling and alignment and a decrease in waviness. These new and rich data sets may be used to re-visit prior experimental measurements of these PNC electrical, thermal and mechanical properties, *e.g.*, the large and nonlinear increase in thermal conductivity at high packing is attributable to decreased waviness and increased bundling. The results reported here show that electron tomography is a powerful tool in investigating the 3D morphology of nanocomposites, making it an essential tool for finding pathways to optimize the multifunctional properties of smart, hierarchical composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The highly attractive properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have long motivated the fabrication of controllable, continuously-drawn, aligned-CNT (A-CNT) nanocomposites, in the expectation that materials with fascinating multifunctional properties [1-3] will be produced. These materials can be used for various applications, such as (but not limited to) structural mechanical reinforcement [4,5], thermal management (thermal interfaces, heaters), [6, 7] and electrical energy management [8]. These exceptional nanocomposite properties are, naturally, dependent on the volume fraction of the A-CNT, and thus increasing the CNT volume fraction without losing their alignment is expected to increase both the axial properties (be it conductivity or stiffness), and the PNC anisotropy, *i.e.* the ratio between the measured axial and the transverse properties. For this purpose, we have previously fabricated ultra-

high volume fraction (V_f) A-CNT epoxy nanocomposites, using a biaxial mechanical densification approach, with excellent control over CNT loading and dispersion.[9] Indeed, these nanocomposites have shown, in the direction of CNT alignment, far superior electrical, mechanical, and thermal properties to those of randomly-dispersed-CNT nanocomposites.[2, 10] In particular, some of the highest electrical and thermal conductivity reported for nanocomposite materials were exhibited. However, even these demonstrated exquisite properties fall short of the theoretical predictions, sometimes by an order of magnitude. This mismatch is hypothesized to be due to differences from the ideal structure, such as bundling, phase separation, structural defects in the CNT walls, inherent and processing-induced waviness of nanotubes, and their evolution with varying V_f [10, 11]. It is thus clear that a quantitative understanding of the nanoscale structure and its relationship to the material properties is needed if accurate, validated models relating structure to properties are to be produced.

However, a detailed quantitative characterization of the morphology is thus far lacking. Electron microscopy-based imaging projection techniques, although useful, are inherently 2D and thus their use in extracting the complex 3D structure of the embedded CNTs is limited.[12] Moreover, due to the chemical similarity of the matrix and filler phases (carbon in carbon), and uncertainties involved in determining CNT density, V_f measurement by conventional weight fraction based techniques such as thermogravimetric analysis is nearly impossible [13].

Figure 1: Volume-rendered reconstructions of (a) 0.44 % (b) 2.6 % (c) 4 % and (d) 6.9 % V_f of A-CNT nanocomposites. The size of reconstructed volumes are (a) 969 nm \times 952 nm \times 324 nm (b) 850 nm \times 840 nm \times 152 nm (c) 848 nm \times 836 nm \times 177 nm and (d) 764 nm \times 841 nm \times 211 nm.

Here, we demonstrate the use of 3D electron tomography for accurate, quantitative, morphological characterization of aligned CNT-filled polymers of V_f 's varying over an order of magnitude (0.44%,

2.6%, 4%, and 6.9%). The high-resolution visualizations thus obtained are used to quantify the Vf, the degree of alignment and waviness, network and the bundle structure. This quantification protocol is a first step towards establishing structure-property relationships in these important material systems. This work is based on Natarajan et. al. “The Evolution of Carbon Nanotube Network Structure in Unidirectional Nanocomposites Resolved by Quantitative Electron Tomography” (*ACS Nano*, submitted 2014) [14] and the details regarding the fabrication, imaging and reconstruction methods are given there. These methods yield 3D visualizations of the nanocomposites as shown in **Figure 1**.

2 MAIN RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dependence of the CNT morphology on Vf is strongly correlated to the changes in material properties [14]. Because of the mechanical densification process, CNTs bundle on different length scales under the effect of short-range van der Waals attractions, and the bundles grow larger as Vf is increased. The Vf of the largest network, which dominates electric and thermal behavior, increases with the increase in overall CNT Vf, up to 4 %, and at higher CNT loading (6.9 %) becomes a cluster containing nearly 50% of the total CNT volume (**Figure 2**). This clustering also increases the density of CNT-CNT contacts, increasing conductivity (electrical and thermal) by creating better pathways for charge carriers and phonons through the material, until these pathways dominate the material transport properties at sufficiently high Vfs. Since the change in number of CNT-CNT contact is non-linear, this trend has significant implications for electrical and thermal transport in such nanofiber networks, as well as failure through and around these CNT bundles.

Figure 2: 3D network-analyzed, volume-rendered reconstructions of (a) 0.44 % (b) 2.6 % (c) 4 % and (d) 6.9 % Vf of A-CNT nanocomposites obtained from sample volumes shown in Figure 1. Individual clusters are identified by unique colors. The white cluster is the largest network in each volume.

The anisotropy in aligned nanofiber based materials is strongly dependent on the degree of alignment. Thus, improved alignment should result in superior axial mechanical properties and increased anisotropy in transport properties. Since the alignment improves with increasing Vf due to

both the increased steric interactions between tubes and the increased level of bundling (**Figure 3**), the enhanced (and nonlinear) effect of Vf on anisotropic properties [2, 10] is further explained.

Figure 3: Orientation analysed, volume-rendered reconstructions of a) 0.44 % (b) 2.6 % (c) 4 % and (d) 6.9 % Vf of A-CNT polymer nanocomposites (A-PNCs) obtained from sample volumes shown in Figure 1. The NTs are color-coded according to the orientation color map from -90° to $+90^\circ$ shown in the inset in (a).

3 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we demonstrate here finely tuned and almost automated tomography image acquisition and analysis methods used in the study of CNT-polymer nanocomposites. The techniques illustrated here can also be used on other low-contrast carbon nanocomposites, including other types of carbon nanofibers and most polymers. The improved quality of the tomographic reconstructions yield a rich, quantitative data set, that can be used to accurately determine Vf, alignment, bundle/network topology, and detailed 3D waviness. Used on mechanically densified A-CNT based nanocomposite, these measurements explain the non-linear effect of CNT volume fraction on previously measured material properties. More broadly, such datasets can produce quantitative understanding of the gap between the expected and measured performance of CNT-based nanocomposites and will enable, eventually, optimized processing methods so that multifunctional materials can indeed be fabricated.

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